

SOCIOECONOMIC MEASURE: A Relativist Perspective on Debt Crisis Management

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Abstract

This paper introduces a concrete definition of the concept of *measure* in human interaction, highlighting its parallels with the principles of moderation and aesthetic balance, the latter traditionally symbolized by the golden ratio in art and architecture. By applying this definition to socioeconomic behavior, the paper proposes a model to help prevent or mitigate future debt crises. The model aligns with the IMF's balance sheet approach for assessing the *net worth* of economic sectors or national economies. Adopting a relativistic perspective in this context, the paper identifies key conditions for implementing alternative policies for debt crisis management. These policies offer a potential pathway for distressed economies to escape debt traps while preserving their socioeconomic structure and protecting creditors' interests.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The classical concept of *measure*, often linked to moderation, balance, equilibrium,¹ harmony and beauty, has been symbolized by the golden ratio² (ϕ) in architecture and the arts.³ However, in the realm of human interaction, an exact definition of measure remains elusive.⁴ Aristotle's notion of *measure* ($\mu\acute{\epsilon}\tau\rho\nu$) as a “subjective mean” between deficiency ($\acute{\epsilon}\lambda\lambda\epsilon\iota\psi\iota\varsigma$) and excess ($\acute{\upsilon}\pi\epsilon\rho\beta\omicron\lambda\eta$) suggests a balance that is closer to one extreme than the other.⁵ This definition though raises a critical question: *how much* closer to one extreme should this balance be?

To date, no universally accepted formula or “magic number”⁶ has been established for defining *measure* in human behavior and interaction. Despite the insights of great thinkers from Homer⁷ to Kant⁸ and Nietzsche,⁹ a comprehensive and precise definition of *measure* has yet to be articulated.

¹ The economic concept of *equilibrium* differs from the philosophical concept of *measure*. Historical examples show that equilibrium can sometimes lead to hubris. For instance, a war economy during *peacetime* (e.g., the German economy in 1930s) may maintain macroeconomic equilibrium but deviate dangerously from *measure*, potentially leading to national ruin and intertemporal infamy. Conversely, a policy of unilateral disarmament (e.g., as in Cyprus in the first half of 1974) might be conducive to macroeconomic equilibrium but could also be hubristic, as it risks national security.

² Euclid, *Elements*, Book 6, Definition 3.

³ The golden ratio ($\phi \cong 1.6180339$) is the asymptotic limit of the Fibonacci sequence F_{n+1} / F_n . It has inspired thinkers across disciplines like no other number in the history of mathematics (Livio 2002).

⁴ “In the social sciences, law, politics and the behavioral sciences, *measure* is a fuzzy concept” (Pappas 2014, p. 74).

⁵ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, 1106a25–35.

⁶ From a traditional academic perspective, defining measure in human affairs may be impossible; even the golden ratio is an irrational number, defying complete mathematical precision. In general, “*numbers are too crude an instrument by which to know something our eyes know at a glance*” (Sachs 2002).

⁷ The concept of *measure* appears 12 times in *Odyssey* (e.g. Bk. 2, l. 231, Bk. 5, l. 9, Bk. 7, l. 310, Bk. 14, l. 434, Bk. 15, l. 71, Bk. 17, l. 321, Bk. 21, l. 294, and Bk. 22, l. 46). Homer uses the word *aisima* ($\alpha\acute{\iota}\sigma\iota\mu\alpha$) for *measure*, related to *Aisa* ($A\acute{\iota}\tau\sigma\alpha$), the Greek goddess personifying human destiny. In the Homeric context, human actions are *measured* if they remain within predestined bounds. Homer suggests a subjectivist notion of social *measure* by modeling interpersonal relations as interactions between hosts and guests (*Odyssey* 15.68-74): “*Measure is always optimal... One must treat a guest well as long as he is in the house and let him go promptly when he wants to leave.*”

⁸ Kant articulated his *categorical imperative*—i.e., “*act only according to that maxim whereby you can at the same time will that it should become a universal law*” (Kant 1785)—without reference to the concept *measure*, a cornerstone of classical civilization. As consequence, this imperative has been used (and abused) hubristically by totalitarian regimes in the 20th century to the detriment of Western civilization.

Consequently, the persistent ambiguity¹⁰ surrounding the concept of *measure*, coupled with the human impulsive tendency toward excess,¹¹ has left individuals, societies, and nations vulnerable to deviations from *measure*, which often manifest as *hubris* and have contributed to the downfall of economies, states, and empires.¹²

This paper seeks to address this indeterminacy by proposing a concrete definition of the classical concept of *measure* that is applicable to human behavior. The proposed definition is both quantitative and qualitative: it is mathematically precise yet intuitively understandable. It aligns with Aristotle's specifications,¹³ being subjective at the individual level, cultural at the macrosocial level, and adaptable to changing circumstances.

To demonstrate the applicability of this definition, the paper applies it to a socioeconomic context. The definition is derived by dynamically modeling socioeconomic interactions¹⁴ within a simplified Aristotelian dyadic (two-sector

⁹ Friedrich Nietzsche's (and the Great Tragedians') view of *hubris* as a significant deviation from *measure* (Nietzsche 1873) has limited utility without a precise definition of *measure* to determine ex ante—before the intervention of retributive *Nemesis*—whether the deviation is indeed significant (hubristic).

¹⁰ In contemporary lexicography, *measure* is defined as “*due* proportion; *due* restraint,” and so on. However, such tautological definitions are of limited utility as they immediately raise the question: what *exactly* is “*due*”?

¹¹ According to Oudemans and Lardinois (1987, p. 203), “Nature and man have boundaries apportioned to them. But finite beings are unable to stay within these boundaries. They can only exist if they continue to partake of the power which has engendered them... But then power is doubled: on the one hand it is divine, apportioning power; on the other hand it manifests itself in finite entities. It is this duality that engenders the tragic conflict. The power concentrated in finite entities prevents them from accepting the boundaries set to them. They are 'hybrid'. . . From their perspective, they have to stay within their boundaries, but they have to transcend them as well. It is both necessary and impossible to avoid transgression.”

¹² According to Robinson (1987, p. 185), “[Heraclitus'] unified, ordered world of balanced change is also a world in which the ‘laws’ or norms of justice prevail... ‘Justice [Nemesis] will catch up with fabricators of falsehoods and those who bear witness to them’ (fragment 28b) because ‘all human laws are nourished by one [law], the divine [law]’ (fragment 114). Consequently ‘there is a greater need to extinguish hubris than there is a blazing fire’ (fragment 43) because the justice that is cosmic law is the justice of disruption and revolution, of war and violence, not that of balm and healing.”

¹³ Unlike the arithmetic mean, the Aristotelian mean is *subjective* (“*the mean relative to us*” or “τὸ μέσον πρὸς ἡμᾶς”) and applies dynamically to human interaction. Therefore it is not the same for different people, as it is *perceived* subjectively, nor does it remain static, as it evolves with changes in internal states and external conditions (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, *ibid*).

¹⁴ This paper might be considered a “Leibnizian” footnote to Aristotle's work on *measure*: by using the mathematical tools of dynamic analysis—invented simultaneously by Pascal and Leibniz two millennia after Aristotle—this paper presents a dynamic model of basic theoretical constructs of *measured* socioeconomic interaction, in a context laid out by Aristotle in *Nicomachean Ethics* and *Politics*.

or two-class) socioeconomic structure.¹⁵ The model's state variables align with the IMF's *balance sheet approach*¹⁶ for assessing the *net worth* and sustainability of economic sectors or national economies: in this model, the *net worth*¹⁷ (N_i) of each sector (i) in an *open mixed* economy changes over time (t) according to a system of differential equations of the following general form:

$$(1) \quad \dot{N}_i = \mathbf{F}_i(N_i, N_j, t) \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

where \dot{N}_i is the derivative of N_i with respect to time (t). In a *closed* economy, or an *open laissez-faire* economy, the *net worth* changes according to the dynamics of the following autonomous system:

$$(2) \quad \dot{N}_i = \Phi_i(N_i, N_j) \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

The definition of *socioeconomic measure*, derived from these systems (relations 1-2), ensures that the *net worth* of each sector and the broader economy—regardless of its structure (closed, or open laissez-faire, or open mixed)—grows over time along a sustainable development path. Thus, this definition presents a promising policy tool for preventing recessions and avoiding future debt traps driven by excessive indebtedness.

Furthermore, with regard to economies that deviate from *socioeconomic measure* and are thus exposed to the risk of future debt crises, this model specifies the necessary conditions for effective debt crisis management, which may include a minimal yet sufficient debt reduction. Such policies enable distressed economies to escape debt traps while maintaining their socioeconomic cohesion—i.e., their established class structure—and simultaneously safeguarding creditors' interests.

In this framework, the main text of the paper presents a descriptive, metaphorical storyline as a comprehensive theory that incorporates qualitative phase-plane analysis, making it accessible to a general interdisciplinary readership. Source material and background information are primarily included in the footnotes to maintain the streamlined nature of the narrative in the main text. The underlying mathematical details, along with statistical data, have been relegated to the Appendix for readers who are more mathematically inclined.

¹⁵ According to Aristotle, “*politically organized societies (poleis) consist of two classes, the people with no economic resources and those in control of such resources*” (“αἱ πόλεις ἐκ δύο συνεστήκασι μορίων, ἕκ τε τῶν ἀπόρων ἀνθρώπων καὶ τῶν εὐπόρων”) (Aristotle, *Politics* V.1315a: 32-33).

¹⁶ This paper presents a qualitative theory aligned with the IMF's *balance sheet approach*, which is summarized in the Appendix (§1).

¹⁷ In lieu of the IMF's term *net worth*, the term *net wealth* (i.e., total *net* value of assets) may be used in order to avoid logical, historical and ethical pitfalls associated with the accounting term *net worth* when applied to human beings at any level (individual, social, national, regional, or global).

II. STRUCTURE OF THE MODEL

We consider a simplified economy with only two members, a prince and a pauper,¹⁸ who may be perceived as representing the two sectors, such as the public and private sectors, of a two-sector¹⁹ economy. In this model, the *net worth* of each member (i) at any given time (t) changes depending not only on the member's own *net worth*, $N_i(t)$, but also on the *net worth*, $N_j(t)$, of the other member (j) at that time. The model is defined by the following equations, where $\dot{N}_i(t)$ is the derivative of $N_i(t)$ with respect to time (t):

$$(1') \quad \dot{N}_i(t) = (w_i - l_i)N_i(t) + b_i N_j(t) + \gamma_i e^{\rho t} + g_i \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

where: $N_i(t)$, $\rho \in \mathfrak{R}$; $w_i, l_i, b_i, g_i > 0$; $\gamma_i \geq 0$;

$N_i(t)$: *net worth* of member i at time t;

w_i : *work coefficient* of member i;

l_i : *leisure coefficient* of member i;

b_i : *interaction coefficient* of member i;

γ_i : *international information coefficient* of member i;

ρ : *policy factor* (determined by the government);

g_i : *teleonomial term* of member i.

This system (1') is based on the following considerations:

- **Work and Leisure Coefficients** (w_i and l_i respectively): Each member (i) has a work coefficient (w_i) and a leisure coefficient (l_i), which reflect the member's view on the trade-off between work and leisure. These coefficients are assumed to be positive; even in a Robinson-Crusoe economy, where there is no social interaction [$N_j(t) = 0, \forall t$], each member (i) will engage in some work ($w_i > 0$) and enjoy some leisure ($l_i > 0$), because work is necessary to replace depreciating capital, while leisure is considered “the end” of work in the Aristotelian sense.²⁰ The difference

¹⁸ The methodology of using metaphors from the behavior of a single individual or a small group of individuals (e.g., a family) to draw inferences about the socioeconomic dynamics or political affairs of a state, was employed by Aristotle (*Ethics* 1100a4-9; *Economics* 1.1343a, 2.1345b).

¹⁹ The two members (prince and pauper) in this dyadic economy can represent not only the two sectors of a two-sector economy but also two antagonistic countries, or groups of countries in a regional economy (e.g., the G7 versus the rest of the world), and so on. In general, the present (dyadic) model builds analytically on two-sector models (Theobald 1960; Cones 1992; Araujo and Teixeira 2004).

²⁰ According to Aristotle, “*Nature herself... requires that we should be able, not only to work properly, but also to use leisure well... Both are required, but the ultimate choice is for*

between these coefficients is denoted as \mathbf{a}_i (where $\mathbf{a}_i \in \mathfrak{R}$ and $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - l_i$) and termed the *intrinsic coefficient* of that member (i).²¹ Each member (i) is *leisure-oriented* if \mathbf{a}_i is negative,²² *work-oriented* if \mathbf{a}_i is positive,²³ or *intrinsically neutral* if \mathbf{a}_i is zero.²⁴ The product of the *intrinsic coefficients* represents the economy's *intrinsic effect*, $\mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j$.

- **Interaction Coefficient (\mathbf{b}_i):** The reaction coefficient \mathbf{b}_i of each member (i) is referred to as that member's *interaction coefficient*,²⁵ which reflects the impact of interpersonal comparisons on that member, i.e., each member (i) is disposed competitively²⁶ towards the other member (j). The higher the *net worth*, $N_j(t)$, of the other member (j) at a time (t), the more motivated the former member (i) is to increase his/her own net worth, $N_i(t)$, by an amount $\mathbf{b}_i N_j(t)$ at that time. The product of the *interaction coefficients* represents the economy's *demonstration effect*,²⁷ $\mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j$.

leisure rather than work, because the former is the natural end of the latter." (Aristotle, *Politics* 8.1337b:30-35).

- ²¹ Regarding the (intragenerational) constancy of the *intrinsic coefficients* (\mathbf{a}_i), see Appendix (§2), where equations (1') are specified in matrix form (Appendix §2, relation 10).
- ²² In the Aristotelian worldview, work is a means to leisure or *scholē* (*σχολή*, which is the Greek root of the English word *school*), meaning well-used free time that allows one to pursue non-material or idealistic goals (Hemingway 1988 and 1996) such as advancing one's intellect or attaining virtue in civic affairs (De Grazia 1962). Thus, leisure is not necessarily recreational and should not be confused with idleness or "conspicuous leisure" (Veblen 1899).
- ²³ A work-oriented individual may find inherent value in work itself, not merely as a means to acquire material possessions (Weber 1905). Such an individual may even live in a Lockean world, where one must constantly strive to create property and value through creative labor (Locke 1690).
- ²⁴ For statistical examples of leisure-oriented and work-oriented economies, see Appendix (§3).
- ²⁵ In the context of national economies, the terms "*intrinsic coefficient*" (\mathbf{a}_i) and "*interaction coefficient*" (\mathbf{b}_i) can be adapted to "*intrasectoral coefficient*" and "*intersectoral coefficient*" respectively for modeling two economic sectors, or "*national coefficient*" and "*international coefficient*" respectively for modeling interactions between two countries.
- ²⁶ Initially (at time $t = 0$), the pauper's endowment, $N_1(0)$, is less than the prince's endowment, $N_2(0)$, as at points **W** and **W'** in Figures 1-3. Over time (t), the pauper aims to increase $N_1(t)$ to surpass $N_2(t)$ in order to become the prince of the economy, while the prince manages $N_2(t)$ in order to maintain the prince's dominant position in the economy.
- ²⁷ The first attempt to incorporate interpersonal comparisons of consumption levels into utility theory was made by Pigou (1903), who specified a utility function that included as dependent variable a (weighted by a "social distance" factor) sum of others' possessions, as suggested by Fischer (1892). Duesenberry (1949) linked these comparisons to the savings ratio, and Nurkse (1952) extended them to economic growth by applying Duesenberry's approach (interclass comparisons) to international comparisons. Regarding the positive impact of the demonstration effect on productivity, this model assumes that social status is based on material wealth (Hoselitz 1963), drawing on theories of the intergroup relations' impact on motivation (Hagen 1963; Young 1971; Cochran 1971) and their potential effect on welfare policies (Lindbeck, Nyberg and Weibull 1999). Concerning a country's overall

- **International Impact** ($\gamma_i e^{\rho t}$): In an open economy, the term $\gamma_i e^{\rho t}$ accounts for the international influence on the change in the *net worth* of each member (i) at a time (t). The *international information* coefficient, γ_i , represents the degree of access that each member (i) has to international information on consumption standards and investment opportunities.²⁸ The *policy factor*, ρ , is determined by the government.²⁹
- **Teleonomial Term** (\mathbf{g}_i): The significance of \mathbf{g}_i becomes apparent in the context of a closed economy, where information borders are closed ($\gamma_i = 0$). In this scenario, the above dynamic system (relations 1 and 1') takes the reduced form of the following autonomous system of linear differential equations (where $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - \mathbf{l}_i$):³⁰

$$(2') \quad \dot{N}_i - \mathbf{a}_i N_i - \mathbf{b}_i N_j = \mathbf{g}_i \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

By setting \dot{N}_i and N_j equal to zero in relation 2' and solving for N_i , we find:

$$(2'') \quad N_i = -(\mathbf{g}_i / \mathbf{a}_i) = \mathbf{G}_i \quad (i = 1, 2)$$

Ratio \mathbf{G}_i , termed the *autarky net worth* of member i, specifies the level of net worth of each member (i) that, in the absence of social interaction ($N_j = 0$), would satisfy all the needs of that member (i) so that no further change in that member's *net worth* is desirable ($\dot{N}_i = 0$). Consequently, the numerator (\mathbf{g}_i) of \mathbf{G}_i is termed the *teleonomial term* of member i and reflects this member's fundamental life goals—such as building a house or creating an artwork—even in isolation as in a Robinson-Crusoe economy.³¹

motivation, Freeman (1976), following McClelland's (1953) earlier work, found a significant correlation between economic growth and societal motivation. In this model, socioeconomic interaction plays a crucial role in the system's dynamic behavior.

²⁸ In a closed economy, like the former USSR or present-day North Korea, the *international information* coefficient (γ_i) is nearly zero ($\gamma_i \cong 0$). In an isolated economy, such as the Robinson Crusoe economy, that coefficient is exactly zero ($\gamma_i = 0$).

²⁹ In a purely laissez-faire economy with no government intervention, the policy factor equals zero ($\rho = 0$). However in reality, fiscal policies can significantly affect the value of this factor (ρ), e.g., through tariffs, taxation, and investment incentives. In this model, it is assumed that these policies remain stable over time, meaning ρ is constant in the medium term within an intragenerational period.

³⁰ Equations 2' can be represented in matrix form as specified in the Appendix (§4, relation 11).

³¹ The *autarky net worth* (\mathbf{G}_i) reflects the i^{th} -member's perception of the trade-offs between teleonomial needs for net-wealth accumulation (\mathbf{g}_i) and intrinsic needs for both work and leisure time (\mathbf{a}_i). A notable literary example is Robinson Crusoe, who worked constructively on his island only until he achieved a *net worth* equal to \mathbf{G}_i , which represented the net value of his living quarters and surroundings necessary for sustaining an autarkic life in isolation.

Based on these considerations, we specify the following categorizations of an economy regarding its overall motivation and prevailing work ethic:

- Overall Motivation:** In a *high-motivation* economy, the demonstration effect is higher than the intrinsic effect ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j > \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$); in a *low-motivation* economy, this effect is lower than the intrinsic effect ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j < \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$); in a *balanced-motivation* economy this effect is equal to the intrinsic effect ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$).
- Prevailing Work Ethic:** The economy is characterized as *leisure-oriented* if both intrinsic coefficients are negative ($\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < \mathbf{0}$), *work-oriented* if both these coefficients are positive ($\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j > \mathbf{0}$), or *heterogenous* if one of these coefficients is negative but the other is positive ($\mathbf{a}_i < \mathbf{0} < \mathbf{a}_j$), i.e., if the agents are conversely disposed regarding work and leisure, with one agent (i) being leisure-oriented and the other (j) work-oriented.

In special (and rather exceptional) cases, if both of these coefficients are zero ($\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{a}_j = \mathbf{0}$), the economy is characterized as *totally neutral*. If either of these coefficients is zero ($\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{0}$ or $\mathbf{a}_j = \mathbf{0}$), the economy is considered *partially neutral*.

FIGURE 1
High-motivation Leisure-oriented Economy.

III. CLOSED ECONOMY

In accordance with these categorizations, the dynamic behavior of a closed economy—with information borders closed ($\gamma_i = 0$), and the assumption that each member may borrow from and lend to foreigners only indirectly, through the country's banking system—can be graphically outlined by setting $\dot{N}_i = 0$ in equations 2' and solving for N_i (at $\dot{N}_i = 0$):

$$(3) \quad N_i = \mathbf{G}_i + \mathbf{B}_i N_j \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

$$(3') \quad \text{where } \mathbf{B}_i = -(\mathbf{b}_i / \mathbf{a}_i) \quad (i = 1, 2)$$

Ratio \mathbf{B}_i , termed the *status coefficient* of member i , represents the percentage of the other member's net worth (N_j) that, in addition to the former member's *autarky net worth* (\mathbf{G}_i), would satisfy all the needs of that member (i), such that no further change in this member's *net worth* is desirable ($\dot{N}_i = 0$). The product, $\mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{B}_j$, of the two status coefficients is termed the *status effect* of the economy.

Relation 3 defines a *demarcation line*, labeled “ $\dot{N}_i = 0$ ” in Figures 1-3, for each member (i). The intercept of the demarcation line “ $\dot{N}_i = 0$ ” equals the member's *autarky wealth* (\mathbf{G}_i), while its slope is equal to the member's *status coefficient* (\mathbf{B}_i).³² In this context, the dynamics of the system depend on the motivation structure of the economy, as follows:

1. **High-motivation Leisure-oriented Economy** ($\mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j > \mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$): Figure 1 depicts a high-motivation leisure-oriented economy. The horizontal axis measures the *net worth* of the pauper (N_1), while the vertical axis measures the *net worth* of the prince (N_2). The two demarcation lines (“ $\dot{N}_1 = 0$ ” and “ $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ ” respectively) intersect at point \mathbf{E} , representing the system's stationary point ($\mathcal{N}_{12}, \mathcal{N}_{21}$), which lies in the third quadrant.³³

$$(4) \quad \mathcal{N}_i = \frac{\mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{g}_j - \mathbf{a}_j \mathbf{g}_i}{\mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

The numerator in equations 4 is positive because $\mathbf{a}_j < 0$, but the denominator is negative because $\mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j > \mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j$, implying $\mathcal{N}_i < 0$. Furthermore, system 2' entails that for each member (i):

$$(5) \quad \frac{\partial \dot{N}_i(t)}{\partial N_i(t)} \text{ is } \left[\begin{array}{ll} < 0 & \text{if this member (i) is } \mathbf{leisure}\text{-oriented} \quad (\mathbf{a}_i < 0) \\ > 0 & \text{if this member (i) is } \mathbf{work}\text{-oriented} \quad (\mathbf{a}_i > 0) \\ = 0 & \text{if this member (i) is intrinsically } \mathbf{neutral} \quad (\mathbf{a}_i = 0) \end{array} \right]$$

³² As depicted in Figure 1, the angle (h_i) of the demarcation line (“ $\dot{N}_i = 0$ ”) of each member (i) with the (dashed) vertical line to the N_i -axis at intersection point \mathbf{G}_i is equal the arctangent of the member's status coefficient: $h_i = \arctan(\mathbf{B}_i)$.

³³ As to the negative net worth of the public sector in EU27 and the U.S., see Appendix (§5).

This information enables us to draw a set of directional arrows,³⁴ such as the small vertical (green) and horizontal (blue) arrows in Figure 1. Consistent with the directional arrows, we may sketch a series of streamlines,³⁵ also known as phase paths, depicted by solid (red) curved arrows in Figure 1, each mapping out the dynamic movement of the system from a selected initial point (e.g., the streamline starting from point **W** in Figure 1).

The stationary point (**E**) has a pair of *stable branches* (**HE** and **H'E** in Figure 1) that flow consistently and directly toward this point, and also has a pair *unstable branches* (**ED** and **ED'** in Figure 1) that flow consistently and directly away from it. These stable branches comprise the (convergent) *saddle path*³⁶ (**HH'** in Figure 1) which passes through this point (**E**) that is characterized as a *saddle point*, i.e., it behaves as an *attractor* for some trajectories and a *repeller* for others. Specifically:

- If initially, at time $t = 0$, the members' net worths, $N_1(0)$ and $N_2(0)$, are depicted by a point lying on a stable branch, the economy will head directly and consistently toward the stationary point (**E**); once it reaches this point, equilibrium prevails, i.e., $N_i(t) = \mathcal{N}_i$, for each member (i) for all t thereafter.
- If the initial net worths, $N_1(0)$ and $N_2(0)$, are depicted by a point that lies on the unstable branch northeast [southwest] of the stationary point (**E**), the economy will move along this branch in a northeastern [southwestern] direction, causing the net worth of the economy, $N_1(t) + N_2(t)$, to be increasing [decreasing] in the long run.
- If the initial net worths, $N_1(0)$ and $N_2(0)$, are depicted by a point that lies to the right of the (convergent) saddle path *and* to the right or left of *both* demarcation lines (such as point **W** in Figure 1), the streamline starting at this point (**W**) initially flows closer to the stationary point (**E**).

³⁴ The negative partial derivative of \dot{N}_1 with respect to N_1 in leisure-oriented economies (where $a_i < 0$) implies that as we move from west [south] to east [north] in Figure 1, i.e., as N_1 [N_2] increases, \dot{N}_1 [\dot{N}_2] decreases, so that the sign of \dot{N}_1 [\dot{N}_2] passes through three stages, in the order $+$, 0 , $-$. Therefore, we append the plus sign on the left [below] and the minus sign on the right of [above] the " $\dot{N}_1 = 0$ " [" $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ "] demarcation line. Based on these plus and minus signs, a set of directional arrows—like the blue [green] horizontal [vertical] arrows in Figures 1-3—can be drawn to indicate the intertemporal movement of N_1 [N_2] in the four areas delineated on the phase plane by the two intersecting demarcation lines (Figures 1-2), or in the three areas delineated by the two parallel demarcation lines (Figure 3).

³⁵ The net worth, $N_i(t)$, of each member (i) at any time (t), depicted by a point on a streamline in Figures 1-3, can be determined by solving the autonomous system of a closed economy, as specified in the Appendix (§6, relations 12 and 14).

³⁶ For the algebraic expression of the saddle path, see Appendix (§7, relation 15).

However, once it crosses a demarcation line (e.g., at point **p** on the “ $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ ” line in Figure 1) it flows in a northeastern direction converging to the unstable branch (**ED'** in Figure 1), indicating that the net worth of the economy will ultimately be increasing in the long run.³⁷

- Conversely, if the initial net worths, $N_1(0)$ and $N_2(0)$, are depicted by a point that lies to the left of the saddle path *and* to the right or left of *both* demarcation lines (such as point **W'** in Figure 1), the streamline initially flows closer to the stationary point (**E**), effecting a *temporary* increase³⁸ in the net worth of one member and a simultaneous decrease in the net worth of the other member (e.g., as in the segment **W'p'** of the streamline in Figure 1). However, as soon as the streamline crosses a demarcation line (e.g., at point **p'** in Figure 1) it flows in a southwestern direction, converging to the unstable branch (**ED** in Figure 1), indicating that the net worth of the economy will ultimately be decreasing in the long run.

FIGURE 2
Low-motivation Leisure-oriented Economy.

³⁷ Necessary conditions for a high-motivation leisure-oriented economy to grow in the long run are specified in the Appendix (§8, relations 16.a-b).

³⁸ For a statistical example of temporary improvement in the EU's net worth before it worsens over the long term, see Appendix (§9).

In this context, the area to the left of the saddle path is termed the economy's *debt-overhang area* or *hubris area* (the grey area in Figure 1), which depicts the specter of a debt crisis: once the economy is caught within this area, it follows an irreversible debt-overhang process (Sachs 1990, 2002) resulting in the deterioration of the net worth of both members in the long run (in the grey-grid part of the hubris area below the stationary point in Figure 1), although the net worth of one member *may* increase temporarily as shown above.

A shock to stock variables, e.g. a withdrawal of investor confidence, might entrap the economy in the hubris area (e.g., by repositioning it from \mathbf{W} to \mathbf{W}' in Figure 1), especially if the economy is initially outside but close to that area (e.g., at point \mathbf{W} in Figure 1). Consequently, this economy is exposed to the risk of a future debt crisis.

2. **Low-motivation Leisure-oriented Economy** ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j < \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$): Figure 2 depicts a low-motivation leisure-oriented economy. The stationary point lies in the first quadrant (point \mathbf{E} in Figure 2), as both the numerator and the denominator on the right side of equations 4 are positive. Moreover, all branches (HE, H'E, DE, D'E in Figure 2) are convergent.³⁹ Thus, this point is a globally *stable node*, as all streamlines flow towards it: all initial vectors converge directly or asymptotically to the equilibrium vector (\mathcal{N}_{12} , \mathcal{N}_{21}), which serves as the *attractor* in an infinite *basin of attraction*, i.e., in the entire two-dimensional space of potential initial vectors.

Consequently there is no *hubris area* in this system, meaning this economy is not exposed to the risk of a future debt crisis. For instance, even if this economy is initially a net debtor (e.g., at points \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{W}' in Figure 2), it will reverse its debt status (from net debtor to net creditor) in the long run.

However, this type of socio-economic hedging (low level of the demonstration effect) against a future debt crisis, limits potential gains from continuous growth in the long run: once the stationary point (\mathbf{E}) is reached in the first quadrant, the same weak impact of the demonstration effect that shields the economy from overborrowing will prevent it from expanding any further.⁴⁰

3. **Positively Balanced Economy** ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$): Inspection of equations 4 reveals that the stationary point (\mathcal{N}_1 , \mathcal{N}_2) of the system vanishes to infinity as the demonstration effect ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j$) approaches the intrinsic effect ($\mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$). Specifically, when $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$:

³⁹ Both eigenvalues—derived from the (characteristic) equation of the system (see Appendix, §6, relation 13)—of a low-motivation leisure-oriented economy (Figure 2), are negative.

⁴⁰ For historical examples of closed low-motivation leisure-oriented economies, see Appendix (§10).

- (6.a) If $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j > \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$, then $\mathcal{N}_i \rightarrow -\infty$ as $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j \rightarrow \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$. $(i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$
- (6.b) If $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j < \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$, then $\mathcal{N}_i \rightarrow +\infty$ as $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j \rightarrow \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$. $(i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$

Statement 6.a implies that a high-motivation leisure-oriented economy may avoid a future debt spiral if the demonstration effect is sufficiently close (from above) to the intrinsic effect. Graphically, the closer the demonstration effect is to the intrinsic effect, the further the convergent branches (HE and H'E in Figure 1) are from the origin in a southwestern direction, and thus the further the hubris area is from the origin in this direction. Similarly, statement 6.b implies that a low-motivation leisure-oriented economy may avoid economic stagnation if the demonstration effect is sufficiently close (from below) to the intrinsic effect. Graphically, the closer the demonstration effect is to the intrinsic effect, the further the stationary point (**E** in Figure 2) is from the origin in a northeastern direction.

FIGURE 3
Positively Balanced Economy.

In the limiting case where the demonstration effect is equal to the intrinsic effect, or equivalently where the status effect equals unity (i.e., where the stationary point vanishes to infinity, as depicted in Figure 3), the economy is not exposed to the risk of a future debt crisis: a hubris area does not appear in this case. Moreover, the forces of the system result in long-term growth in the economy's net worth, regardless of the initial endowment, $N_i(0)$, of each

member (i) and irrespectively of future shocks to stock variables: The economy will absorb such shocks (e.g., like one that might shift the economy from point \mathbf{W} to point \mathbf{W}' in Figure 3) and will follow a new path (e.g., the streamline starting at \mathbf{W}' in Figure 3) of economic growth. In this context, the degenerate-equilibrium case ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$) of a leisure-oriented economy ($\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$) represents an economy that is perfectly (completely) shielded from both indebtedness and stagnation.

Although such *positively balanced*⁴¹ motivational structure is rather conceptual, it still serves as a reminder that both the debt and stagnation traps (Figures 1 and 2 respectively) can be avoided if a leisure-oriented economy is marked by a (cultural) motivational balance, such that $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j \cong \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$.

4. **Exposed Economies:** All other types of economies—whether *work-oriented* ($\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j > 0$), *counteractive* ($\mathbf{a}_i < 0$ or $\mathbf{a}_j > 0$), *partially neutral* ($\mathbf{a}_i = 0$ or $\mathbf{a}_j = 0$), or *totally neutral* ($\mathbf{a}_i = 0$ and $\mathbf{a}_j = 0$)—share a common characteristic: they are all exposed to the risk of a future debt spiral, indicated by the presence of a hubris area in their graphical depiction. This exposure exists even in cases where the motivation is low ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j < \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$) or balanced ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$) in such economies.⁴²

IV. OPEN LAISSEZ-FAIRE ECONOMY

In a laissez-faire economy, where information borders are open ($\gamma_i > 0$) and there is no government intervention ($\mathbf{p} = 0$), the dynamic system 1' simplifies to an autonomous system of linear differential equations (where $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - l_i$; $\gamma_i > 0$):⁴³

$$(7) \quad \dot{N}_i - \mathbf{a}_i N_i - \mathbf{b}_i N_j = \mathbf{g}_i + \gamma_i \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

By setting $\dot{N}_i = 0$ in equations (7) and solving for N_i we derive the equations of the demarcation lines of a laissez-faire economy:

$$(8) \quad N_i = \mathbf{G}_i + \mathbf{\Gamma}_i + \mathbf{B}_i N_j \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

$$(8') \quad \text{where } \mathbf{\Gamma}_i = -(\gamma_i / \mathbf{a}_i) \quad (i = 1, 2)$$

⁴¹ The term “*positively balanced*” (Figure 3), as opposed to “*negatively balanced*” (Figure 11 in the Appendix), implies that the (parallel) demarcation lines of the economy are *positively* (upward) sloped.

⁴² In the Appendix, Figures 9 and 10 depict the dynamics of *work-oriented* economies that have a *high-motivation* (Figure 9) or *low-motivation* (Figure 10) structure; moreover Figure 11 depicts a *negatively balanced* economy (where $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$ and $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j > 0$). A hubris area (in grey color) is embedded in all of them.

⁴³ For the expression of relation 7 in matrix form, see Appendix (§11, relation 17).

Ratio Γ_i , termed the *information effect* on member i , represents the impact of information (γ_i) on this member (i), internalized according to the member's perception (\mathbf{a}_i) of the trade-offs between work and leisure.

These equations (8) are analogous to the equations (3) for the demarcation lines in a closed economy: The slope (\mathbf{B}_i) of each member's demarcation line in an open laissez-faire economy is identical to the slope in a closed economy. Additionally, in open laissez-faire economies, the partial derivative of \dot{N}_i with respect to N_i is negative if they are leisure-oriented and positive if they are work-oriented, as in closed economies (by relation 5). Therefore, the dynamics, as depicted by directional arrows in both types of economies, are similar.⁴⁴ Consequently, all inferences drawn from the phase-plane analysis for closed economies also apply to open laissez-faire economies.

The only difference between these economies lies in the intercept of each demarcation line. In a closed economy, the intercept equals the member's *autarky net worth* (\mathbf{G}_i) according to equations 3. In a laissez-faire economy, however, the intercept is equal to the member's *autarky net worth* (\mathbf{G}_i) augmented by the *information effect* (Γ_i) on this member (i), as per equations 8. Thus, the transformation of a closed leisure-oriented economy into an open laissez-faire economy entails the following effects:

1. **Open Laissez-Faire High-Motivation Leisure-oriented Economy:** In an open laissez-faire economy that is leisure-oriented ($\mathbf{a}_i < 0$), the information effect on each member (i) is positive ($\Gamma_i > 0$). Consequently, if a closed high-motivation leisure-oriented economy (Figure 1) opens its information borders, both demarcation lines will shift, the “ $\dot{N}_1 = 0$ ” line horizontally to the right, and the “ $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ ” line vertically upward. As a result, the stationary point in the third quadrant will shift in a southwestern direction, while the saddle path (HH in Figure 1), which forms the rightmost border of the hubris area, will also move in this direction, as it passes through the new stationary point. This further distancing of the hubris area from the origin, due to open information borders, reduces the economy's exposure to a future debt crisis. Therefore, information dissemination across borders, without government intervention, partially shields a high-motivation leisure-oriented economy from indebtedness.
2. **Open Laissez-faire Low-Motivation Leisure-Oriented Economy:** Similarly, if a closed low-motivation leisure-oriented economy (Figure 2) opens its information borders, both demarcation lines “ $\dot{N}_1 = 0$ ” and the “ $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ ” will likewise shift, to the right and upward respectively. As a result, the

⁴⁴ In this model, a change in the economy's motivation structure—specifically, an increase in the interaction coefficient (\mathbf{b}_i) of each member (i)—resulting from opening the country's information borders is assumed to be absent, as specified in Relation 1' and as discussed in the Appendix (§12).

stationary point of the economy will shift in a northeastern direction. At the new position, the net worth of the economy ($\mathcal{N}_{12} + \mathcal{N}_{21}$) will be higher than before the opening of its information borders. Therefore, information dissemination across borders, without government intervention, increases the net worth⁴⁵ of a low-motivation leisure-oriented economy.

3. **Open Laissez-faire Positively Balanced Economy:** If a *positively balanced* closed economy (Figure 3) opens its information borders, then both demarcation lines “ $\dot{N}_1 = 0$ ” and the “ $\dot{N}_2 = 0$ ” will likewise shift, to the right and upward respectively. In their their new positions, they will remain parallel. Thus, opening the information borders of a *positively balanced* closed economy has no effect on its (zero) exposure to indebtedness: a hubris area does not exist in an open laissez-faire *positively balanced* economy either.
4. **Exposed Economies:** The exposure of all other types of closed economies (discussed in section III.4) to the risk of future debt crisis, as marked by a hubris area, will be reduced if they open their information borders, as described in Section IV.1 above. The only exception is a *totally neutral* economy,⁴⁶ whose exposure to a future debt crisis remains unchanged before and after the opening of its information borders. In general, if a closed economy is exposed to a future debt crisis, it will remain exposed to such a crisis after its transformation to an open laissez-faire economy, but such exposure will be reduced as a result of opening its information borders.

V. OPEN MIXED ECONOMY

An open mixed economy, characterized by open information borders ($\gamma_i > 0$) and government intervention ($\rho \neq 0$), is described by relation 1'. By setting $\dot{N}_i(t) = 0$ and $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - \mathbf{l}_i$ in this relation and solving for $N_i(t)$, we derive the equations of the demarcation lines at a point in time (t):

$$(9) \quad N_i(t) = \mathbf{G}_i + \Gamma_i e^{\rho t} + \mathbf{B}_i N_j(t) \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

As shown in equations (9), the slope (\mathbf{B}_i) of the demarcation line of each member (i) is constant, as in both closed economies (equations 3) and open laissez-faire economies (equations 8).

However, in an open mixed economy, the N_i -axis intercept ($\mathbf{G}_i + \Gamma_i e^{\rho t}$) is a function of time (t), causing the demarcation line of each member i to shift in

⁴⁵ For the algebraic specification of the increase in an economy's net worth due to opening its information borders, see Appendix (§13, relation 18).

⁴⁶ Figure 12 in the Appendix depicts a completely neutral economy ($\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{a}_j = 0$), which is also marked by the presence of a hubris area (see also footnote 42).

the direction of the N_i -axis over time.⁴⁷ Such an economy's stationary point moves over time progressively further away from the origin over time.⁴⁸ In general, the following inferences are drawn regarding open mixed economies:⁴⁹

1. **Contractionary Policy ($\rho < 0$):** If $\rho < 0$ in an open mixed economy, its dynamics will eventually converge to those of a closed economy (where $\Gamma_i e^{\rho t} = 0$), because $\rho < 0$ implies that $\lim(\mathbf{G}_i + \Gamma_i e^{\rho t}) = \mathbf{G}_i$, as $t \rightarrow \infty$.
2. **Expansionary Policy ($\rho > 0$):** The effects of expansionary policy ($\rho > 0$) in an open mixed economy are summarized below, from the analytical viewpoint of the transformation of an open laissez-faire economy into an open mixed economy:
 - 2.1. **Risk of Future Debt Crisis:** If an open laissez-faire economy is exposed to the risk of a future debt crisis (as discussed in sections IV.1 and IV.4), its exposure will diminish after its transformation into an open mixed economy. The saddle path, which forms the rightmost border of the hubris area, will be continuously repositioned further away from the origin—in a leftward or southwestern or downward direction, depending on the structure of the economy—over time (t) if the government's policy is expansionary ($\rho > 0$).
 - 2.2. **Risk of Future Stagnation:** If an open laissez-faire economy is exposed to the risk of future stagnation in the economy's net worth (as discussed in section IV.2), this exposure *may* diminish over time after its transformation into an open mixed economy: its stationary point will be continuously repositioned further from the origin in a northeastern direction over time if the government's policy is expansionary ($\rho > 0$).
 - 2.3. **Shielding from Indebtedness and Stagnation:** If an open laissez-faire economy is *positively balanced* (as discussed in section IV.3), its transformation into an open mixed economy does not affect its (zero) exposure to the risks of debt crisis and stagnation. However, an expansionary government policy ($\rho > 0$) will determine the economy's growth rate, which tends toward ρ in the long run.

⁴⁷ For a review and graphical depiction of the movement of each demarcation line (which, as it moves over time, forms a *demarcation surface*) in the three-dimensional space (where the third dimension is time t), and the concomitant movement of the stationary point (which, as it moves over time, delineates a *stationary path*, where the two *demarcation surfaces* intersect), see Appendix (§14, Figure 7).

⁴⁸ For the algebraic expression of the stationary point $[\mathcal{N}_i(t), \mathcal{N}_j(t)]$ over time (t) in an open mixed economy, see Appendix (§15, relations 19-20).

⁴⁹ For the general solution of the non-autonomous system of an open mixed economy, see Appendix (§16, relation 22).

VI. SOCIOECONOMIC MEASURE

In general, an economy can be effectively shielded from both indebtedness and stagnation if it is *positively balanced*, i.e., if it fulfils two key conditions: (1) its intrinsic effect is equal to its demonstration effect, *and* (2) the economy is *leisure-oriented*. Specifically, an economy will be safeguarded against these risks if:

1. In economic decisions, the members (sectors) of the economy consider equally *socioeconomic standards*, representing extrinsic patterns of behavior, and their intrinsic *dispositions*, reflecting deeply-rooted personal and cultural traits. This balance is achieved when the *demonstration effect* equals the *intrinsic effect* ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$) or, equivalently, when the *status effect* equals unity ($\mathbf{B}_i\mathbf{B}_j = 1$).
2. The economy is uniformly *leisure-oriented*, meaning that the society values leisure time highly for culturally cohesive activities, with *all* members' (sectors') intrinsic coefficients being negative ($\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$).

At a national level, the optimal condition for shielding an economy from indebtedness and recession is termed *socioeconomic measure*, which is defined as follows:⁵⁰

Socio-economic measure is a condition of valuing national traits and international standards equally in socioeconomic behavior in a country that is uniformly committed to cultural development.

VII. SUSTAINABILITY

From a socioeconomic or an environmental perspective, a *positively balanced* economy *may* be sustainable, as outlined below:

1. **Equity:** In a *positively balanced* economy, the *relative* net worth of each member (i), as a percentage of the net worth of the other member (j), tends to align with the former's status coefficient (\mathbf{B}_i) in the long run,⁵¹ i.e., this ratio, $N_i(t)/N_j(t)$, approaches asymptotically this coefficient (\mathbf{B}_i) as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

⁵⁰ The (general) definition of *measure* in human behavior is specified epigrammatically in the Appendix (§17), in line with the above (particular) definition of *socioeconomic measure*.

⁵¹ As summarized in the Appendix (§18), in a positively balanced *closed* or *open laissez-faire* economy, the *attractor* is the demarcation line " $\dot{N}_i = 0$ " of the member (i) with the *lower* status coefficient ($\mathbf{B}_i < \mathbf{B}_j$); likewise, in a positively balanced *open mixed* economy, the *attractor* is the demarcation surface " $\dot{N}_i(t) = 0$ " of the member (i) with the *lower* status coefficient ($\mathbf{B}_i < \mathbf{B}_j$).

Therefore the share of each member (i) in the economy's net worth in the long run can be expressed in terms of this member's status coefficient (\mathbf{B}_i): This share tends to the ratio $\mathbf{B}_i / (\mathbf{B}_i + 1)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

These limits, termed *equity limits*,⁵² demonstrate that, over time, the distribution of the economy's net worth increasingly reflects the personal *value system* ($\mathbf{w}_i, l_i, \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{b}_i$), represented by the status coefficient (\mathbf{B}_i), of each member (i). In Aristotelian terms, this “proportionate equality”⁵³ in the distribution of the net worth in a *positively balanced* economy—as proportionality is *subjectively* perceived by each member—is achieved in the long run, regardless of whether the economy is closed, or open laissez-faire, or open-mixed.

2. **Resource Utilization:** In *positively balanced* economies, whether they are closed, or open laissez-faire, or open mixed with contractionary or neutral government policies ($\rho \leq 0$), the growth rate remains positive and asymptotically approaches zero from above⁵⁴ over time.⁵⁵

However, in an open mixed economy with expansionary government policy ($\rho > 0$), the growth rate approaches asymptotically the *policy factor* (ρ),⁵⁶ which represents the long-term rate of change in the economy's net worth. This type of growth increases the demand for natural resource utilization across the economy's sectors continuously and exponentially.

VIII. EFFECTIVE WEALTH REDISTRIBUTION

The preceding analysis (Sections VI-VII) focuses on *positively balanced* economies that are perfectly shielded from both indebtedness and stagnation. In reality, however, most economies exhibit motivation structures that are not

⁵² The *equity limits* are specified algebraically in the Appendix (§19, relations 24a-b).

⁵³ According to Aristotle, “It is important that both [classes] think that they are prevented from committing *any* act of injustice against each other” (“μάλιστα μὲν ἀμφοτέρους ὑπολαμβάνειν δεῖ ... τοὺς ἑτέρους ὑπὸ τῶν ἑτέρων ἀδικεῖσθαι μηδέν”) (Aristotle, *Politics* V.1315a:45), “and we must first assume the starting-point, that many forms of constitution have come into existence with everybody agreeing as to what is *just*, i.e., *proportionate equality*” (“δεῖ δὲ πρῶτον ὑπολαβεῖν τὴν ἀρχὴν, ὅτι πολλὰ γεγένηνται πολιτεῖαι πάντων μὲν ὁμολογούντων τὸ δίκαιον καὶ τὸ κατ’ ἀναλογίαν ἴσον”) (Aristotle, *Politics* V.1301a:26-27).

⁵⁴ In recent bibliography, the phenomenon of economic slowdowns of (positive) growth rates in advanced and highly indebted economies in the long run, is analyzed from different perspectives (Burgess 2021; Moyer 2023; Piketty 2014).

⁵⁵ The rate of change in the economy's net worth at point in time (t) is derived in the Appendix (§20, relations 26-27).

⁵⁶ The rate of change in the economy's indebtedness that is trapped within the hubris area is summarily discussed in the Appendix (§21, relation 28).

positively balanced and are thus vulnerable to the risk of future debt crises. This vulnerability is indicated by the presence of a *hubris area* in their graphical representation (Figure 1 above and Figures 9-10 in the Appendix).

When a high-motivation economy becomes entrapped within its hubris area, wealth redistribution can serve as a policy tool to reposition the economy outside of this area. The key policy questions surrounding such redistribution are:

- Is *effective* wealth redistribution economically feasible?
- Which sector should be favored?
- What is the appropriate amount of wealth redistribution?
- Should the implementation of the redistribution be gradual (as in policies of mild adjustment) or instantaneous (as in shock therapy)?

In an entrapped high-motivation economy, *effective* wealth redistribution (e.g., from W' to W'' in Figure 1), such that it enables the economy to exit the hubris area, is economically feasible only if the slope of the saddle path differs from -1 . While this condition⁵⁷ is necessary for such redistribution, it is not sufficient on its own.

Beyond this feasibility condition, the choice between populist or liberal wealth redistribution policies—favoring the pauper or the prince, respectively, in this model—depends on the economy's motivational structure:⁵⁸

- If the slope of the saddle path is steeper (i.e., less than -1) with respect to the axis of member i (i.e., the N_i -axis), wealth redistribution should favor that member (i) (e.g., the pauper in Figure 1).
- Conversely, if the slope is greater than -1 , the wealth redistribution should favor the other member (j) of the economy (e.g., the prince in Figure 8 in the Appendix).

These conditions highlight the relativistic nature of the model. In either case—whether *populist* or *liberal* redistribution policies—the redistribution must be of sufficient magnitude⁵⁹ and implemented instantaneously⁶⁰ to be *effective*.

⁵⁷ The feasibility condition for *effective* wealth redistribution is specified algebraically, along with its economic interpretation, in the Appendix (§22, relation 29).

⁵⁸ The criterion for choosing between populist or liberal wealth redistribution policies is presented algebraically in the Appendix (§23).

⁵⁹ The amount of *effective* wealth redistribution is specified algebraically in the Appendix (§24).

⁶⁰ The critical importance of instantaneity (as opposed to *gradual* or *mild* adjustment) in wealth redistribution is summarized graphically in the Appendix (§25, Figure 13). The argument for large-scale, instantaneous wealth redistribution, as a policy tool to escape a debt trap, aligns with the economic literature on fiscal adjustment for debt crisis resolution (Alesina et al. 2017; Daniel et al. 2006; Mayer and Schnabl 2021; Mian et al. 2021).

IX. SOCIOECONOMIC COHESION

Effective wealth redistribution is also contingent on the political will to implement such a policy, which may need to be drastic and executed in a single phase. Political disincentives for such redistribution often arise from concerns about its socioeconomic consequences, such as a reversal of the established class structure. For example, in Figure 1, after *effective* wealth redistribution repositions the entrapped economy from point **W** inside the hubris area to point **W'** outside it, the pauper becomes the new “prince” (the wealthier sector).

However, in Figure 4, where the saddle path is relatively steep with respect to the N_1 -axis, the effective wealth redistribution from point **W** to point **W'**—in favor of member 1 (the pauper)—does not entail a reversal of the class structure. This is because the saddle path is positioned to the right of the intersection (η) of the *wealth-redistribution* line with the *egalitarian-distribution* line. The former passes through the economy's position (**W**) and forms a 135° angle with the N_1 -axis, while the latter passes through the origin at a 45° angle with the same axis. Such redistribution is characterized as *cohesively effective*.⁶¹

FIGURE 4
Cohesively Effective Wealth Redistribution (from **W** to **W'**).

⁶¹ The socio-political feasibility conditions for *cohesively effective* wealth redistribution are specified algebraically in the Appendix (§26, Relations 31-32’).

X. COMPREHENSIVE DEBT REDUCTION

If the *saddle path* of an entrapped economy is relatively steep with respect to the N_1 -axis and is positioned to the right of the intersection (η) of the *wealth-redistribution* line and the *egalitarian-distribution* line (as depicted in Figure 5), then an *effective* wealth redistribution in favor of member i (e.g., from point W to point W'' in Figure 5) would not be socioeconomically *cohesive*.

Under these conditions, a policy mix of wealth redistribution and debt reduction may enable the economy to escape its debt trap without disrupting its socioeconomic class structure, while simultaneously minimizing creditor losses due to the reduction.

As shown in Figure 5, this policy mix, termed *comprehensive debt reduction* (or, equivalently, *conditional debt restructuring*), would reposition the economy from point W inside the hubris area to point W' outside this area, just above the intersection of the *saddle path* and the *egalitarian-distribution* line. This intersection (point δ in Figure 5), termed the *saddle-path egalitarian point*,⁶² is central to this policy, which includes the following three actions:⁶³

FIGURE 5
Conditional Debt Reduction.

⁶² The net worth of each sector when the economy is positioned on the *saddle-path egalitarian point* is specified algebraically in the Appendix (§27).

⁶³ The three components of *comprehensive debt reduction* are specified algebraically in the Appendix (§28).

1. **Wealth redistribution**, in favor of the underprivileged sector (member 1 Figure 5), that repositions the economy from point \mathbf{W} to point ξ on the *wealth-redistribution* line within the hubris area. Both ξ and the *saddle-path egalitarian point* (δ) share the same coordinate, $\delta_2(t)$, on the axis of the other sector (N_2 -axis in the figure).
2. **Debt reduction**, also in favor of the underprivileged sector, by an amount represented by the horizontal distance (the red-dashed line segment in Figure 5) between points ξ and δ , which repositions the economy horizontally from point ξ to the *saddle-path egalitarian point* (δ).
3. **Debt reduction**, in favor of the other (privileged) sector, by a marginal (small) amount u , that repositions the economy vertically from the *saddle-path egalitarian point* (δ) to point \mathbf{W}' outside the hubris area.

These three components of comprehensive debt reduction must all be implemented in a single phase—simultaneously and instantaneously—so that there is no time for the system's dynamics to distort the policy's implementation (as they do in Figure 13 in the Appendix). Only then will the policy be cohesively effective *and* minimize creditor loss⁶⁴ due to debt reduction. As a result, the egalitarian⁶⁵ structure of *comprehensive debt reduction* serves the interests of both creditors and debtors⁶⁶ in the economy.

XI. CONCLUSION

A *positively balanced* economy ensures *socioeconomic cohesion*, as the distribution of net worth across sectors aligns with each sector's value system over the long term. It also promotes positive economic growth with minimal natural resource utilization, as the growth rate approaches zero asymptotically (from above) over time.

However, if the government implements an expansionary economic policy to achieve a higher growth rate, this rate will stabilize at a constant (ρ) in the long run, determined by government policy, leading to exponential growth.

⁶⁴ The creditors' loss due to *comprehensive debt reduction* is specified algebraically in the Appendix (§29).

⁶⁵ Each sector's (egalitarian) net worth, right after the implementation of *comprehensive debt reduction*, is specified algebraically in the Appendix (§30, relations 36a,b).

⁶⁶ Minimizing creditor loss through *comprehensive debt restructuring* serves the interests not only of creditors—considering the tradeoff between financing a debt overhang and forgiving it (Krugman 1988)—but also those of debtors: Evidence suggests that while credit markets may “forgive,” they rarely “forget” (Cruses 2013).

Such growth is unbounded, continually increasing the demand for natural resource utilization across the economy's sectors.

An economy lacking a *positively balanced* motivation structure is vulnerable to sovereign debt crises. If the economy falls into a debt trap—triggered by a sudden loss of creditor confidence—it risks spiraling into a debt crisis. This model prescribes specific policy alternatives for effectively managing such crises, enabling the economy to escape the debt trap while preserving its socioeconomic class structure.

According to the model, the choice between these alternatives depends on the particular conditions of the economy's motivation structure. These alternatives, which minimize or even eliminate creditor losses, include: *wealth redistribution* (without debt reduction), *unconditional debt reduction* (without wealth redistribution),⁶⁷ *wealth redistribution with insignificant debt reduction*,⁶⁸ and *comprehensive debt reduction* (combining wealth redistribution with significant yet minimal debt reduction).⁶⁹

To be cohesively effective, each alternative must be implemented in a single phase—instantaneously in this dynamic model. Furthermore, these conditions determine whether the policy should be liberal, populist, or even egalitarian,⁷⁰ based on the specific requirements and relativist⁷¹ inferences of the model.

⁶⁷ The special case of *unconditional debt reduction*, as a *cohesively effective* policy for debt crisis management, is outlined in the Appendix (§31).

⁶⁸ The special case of wealth redistribution with only negligible debt reduction, as an appropriate policy for debt crisis management, is outlined in the Appendix (§32).

⁶⁹ *Comprehensive debt reduction* aligns with economic literature on the importance of swift debt restructuring with significant haircuts, combined with fiscal consolidation—either directly or indirectly through wealth redistribution—to restore fiscal stability and improve growth trajectories post-crisis (Asonuma & Trebesch, 2016; Das et al. 2012; Guzman and Stiglitz 2016; Patel and Sapriza 2023).

⁷⁰ *Comprehensive debt reduction* involves *temporary* egalitarian restructuring of the economy to safeguard creditor interests by thus minimizing creditor loss. Under particular conditions, such a *temporary* egalitarian reset of a distressed economy aligns with *temporary* egalitarian policies that mark the transition of a peace economy to a war economy in times of total warfare, as elaborated in the Appendix (§33).

⁷¹ This model's *relativist* approach to debt crisis management is summarized *algorithmically* in the Appendix (Figure 14).

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APPENDIX

Supplementary material for the research paper titled
Socioeconomic measure: A relativist perspective on debt crisis management

APPENDIX ABSTRACT

This Appendix is intended for readers who are mathematically inclined. It includes mathematical analysis, statistical data and additional pertinent figures for the paper titled *Socioeconomic measure: A relativist perspective on debt crisis management*.

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1. This paper presents a qualitative theory aligned with the IMF's *balance sheet approach* for diagnosing vulnerabilities in national and regional economies. To quote [Traa](#) and [Carare](#) (2007), “Studying the accumulated stocks of assets and liabilities of a country... can be a supplemental guide to uncover distress. What holds for the country holds for the public sector as well. Many vulnerabilities do not show up in the budget, but become apparent when a public sector balance sheet reflecting all assets and liabilities is constructed. Analyzing the government's *net worth* and what causes it to change can lead to understanding the need for better policies. In recent years, the IMF has increasingly incorporated analysis of stock variables in its monitoring of countries' economies—what is known as the *balance sheet approach* in surveillance ([Allen et al. 2002 and 2007](#); [Rosenberg et. al. 2005](#)).”
2. The *intrinsic coefficient* (\mathbf{a}_i) of each member (i) is constant in this (intragenerational) model, consistent with research on the stability of personality traits ([Edmonds, Goldberg, Hampson and Barckley 2013](#); [Hampson and Goldberg 2006](#); [Soldz and Vaillant 1999](#)) and cultural traits ([Maridal 2013](#); [Stephenson 2023](#)). The constancy of these coefficients is also aligned with the *intertemporal consistency* assumption in consumer choice theory. In this context, setting $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - \mathbf{l}_i$, the system of differential equations (1'), can be expressed in the following matrix form:

$$(10) \quad \dot{\mathbf{N}}(t) - \mathbf{AN}(t) = \mathbf{g} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}e^{\rho t}$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{N}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} N_1(t) \\ N_2(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_1 & \mathbf{b}_1 \\ \mathbf{b}_2 & \mathbf{a}_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_1 \\ \mathbf{g}_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\gamma} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_1 \\ \gamma_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

3. The 40-hour workweek movement, which began as early as 1817 with the guiding ideal “*Eight hours labour, Eight hours recreation, Eight hours rest*” ([Booth 1869](#); [Darwish 2023](#)), indicates a societal shift toward balancing work and leisure. Economies where most of the labor force works more than 40 hours per week are *work-oriented*, such as Japan (75.9%), the US (67.6%) and Switzerland (66.9%). In contrast, economies where less than 20% of the labor force works beyond 40 hours per week, like Finland (16.0%) and Norway (15.8%), may be considered *leisure-oriented* (ILO, Key Indicators – Data is for 2000).
4. The autonomous system of differential equations for modeling a closed economy (relation 2') can be represented in the following matrix form:

$$(11) \quad \dot{\mathbf{N}} - \mathbf{AN} = \mathbf{g}$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{N} = \begin{bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } \mathbf{A} \text{ and } \mathbf{g} \text{ are specified in relation 10 above.}$$

5. The negative *stationary net worth* ($\mathcal{N}_{12} + \mathcal{N}_{21}$) of *high-motivation leisure-oriented* economies (Figure 1), depicted by the *stationary point* ($\mathcal{N}_{12}, \mathcal{N}_{21}$) in the third quadrant, aligns with IMF calculations of the net worth of the public sector in EU27 (see Table I). Additionally, the net worth of the U.S. government has been significantly negative. To quote [Kotlikoff](#) (2010), “Uncle Sam has been misrepresenting the nation's finances for decades. In the process, he has run up an undisclosed bill that makes the financial bailout and economic stimulus spending look paltry... According to David M. Walker, former Chief Comptroller General of the United States, the federal government's current liabilities to Medicare, Social Security and the federal debt total \$56.4 trillion... The current fiscal gap in the

United States is estimated by J. Gokhale of the Cato Institute and K. Smetters of the University of Pennsylvania at \$77 trillion—more than five times the United States' present GDP... There is reason to believe that the \$77 trillion figure would be even larger were the government's future cash flow discounted, taking into account that future benefit payment outlays appear to be more certain than do future tax receipts... Given the magnitude of the fiscal gap, the country is effectively broke... The total gap will amount to nearly \$80 trillion in 2010.”

Intertemporal Net Worth of Public Sector in EU-27 countries

EU-27 countries		Intertemporal net worth of public sector as % of GDP	
Rank*	Country	Finite	Infinite
1	Cyprus	- 494	- 1,793
2	Greece	- 418	- 1,385
3	Luxembourg	- 383	- 1,745
4	Spain	- 307	- 986
5	Slovenia	- 287	- 1,262
6	Czech Rep.	- 256	- 996
7	Romania	- 252	- 1,097
8	Lithuania	- 250	- 857
9	Slovak Rep.	- 243	- 981
10	Netherlands	- 218	- 697
11	Ireland	- 213	- 812
12	Estonia	- 200	- 595
13	Malta	- 188	- 790
14	Austria	- 173	- 514
15	UK	- 172	- 558
16	Belgium	- 156	- 427
17	Germany	- 152	- 484
18	France	- 148	- 339
19	Finland	- 130	- 552
20	Italy	- 110	- 129
21	Portugal	- 106	- 273
22	Poland	- 72	- 140
23	Latvia	- 20	- 28
24	Denmark	- 2	87
25	Bulgaria	0	- 212
26	Sweden	43	- 25
27	Hungary	43	21
Average (weighted)		- 153	- 472

Source: IMF (2010)

*Rank order: Top is worst (most indebted)

TABLE I

6. The net worth, $N_i(t)$, of each member (i) at any time (t), depicted by a point on a streamline in Figures 1-3—where the starting point of the streamline depicts the net worth or *endowment*, $N_i(0)$, of each member (i) at initial time ($t = 0$)—is specified by the general solution of the autonomous system of a closed economy (relation 11), as follows:

$$(12) \quad \begin{bmatrix} N_1(t) \\ N_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{N}_1 \\ \mathcal{N}_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1 e^{r_1 t} \\ \mathbf{n}_2 e^{r_2 t} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1 \\ \mathbf{n}_2 \end{bmatrix} = (\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2)/\beta_{11} & -(\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_1) \\ -(\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2)/\beta_{11} & \mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N_1(0) - \mathcal{N}_1 \\ N_2(0) - \mathcal{N}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

where \mathbf{r}_k ($k = 1, 2$) are the system's two characteristic roots, also called eigenvalues; the stationary net worth (\mathcal{N}_i) of each member (i) is specified by relation 4; and β_{ik} ($k = 1, 2$), are the *adjusted status coefficients* of each member (i):

$$(12') \quad \beta_{ik} = - \frac{\mathbf{b}_i}{\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{r}_k} \quad (i, k) = (1, 2)$$

Each β_{ik} represents the adjustment of the intrinsic coefficient (\mathbf{a}_i) of each member (i)—and consequently (by relation 3') of the member's *status coefficient* (\mathbf{B}_i)—by eigenvalue \mathbf{r}_k so that the characteristic equation (relation 13 below) of the reduced linearization of the autonomous system (relation 11) is equal to zero, making the two equations of the reduced (homogenous) system linearly dependent:

$$(13) \quad \begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{a}_1 & -\mathbf{b}_1 \\ -\mathbf{b}_2 & \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{a}_2 \end{vmatrix} = \mathbf{r}^2 - (\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{a}_1\mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{b}_2 = 0$$

Solving this quadratic equation 13 yields two distinct real eigenvalues ($\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2 \in \Re$), given our assumption of positive interaction coefficients ($\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2 > 0$). Notably, the above general solution (relation 12) is expressed primarily in terms of the variables (or “value system”) of the first member (1). It may also be expressed primarily in terms of the variables (or “value system”) of the second member (2) as follows:

$$(14) \quad \begin{bmatrix} N_1(t) \\ N_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{N}_1 \\ \mathcal{N}_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1/\beta_{21} & 1/\beta_{22} \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1 e^{r_1 t} \\ \mathbf{n}_2 e^{r_2 t} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1 \\ \mathbf{n}_2 \end{bmatrix} = (\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{b}_2 & -(\mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{r}_2) \\ \mathbf{b}_2 & \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{r}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N_1(0) - \mathcal{N}_1 \\ N_2(0) - \mathcal{N}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

7. If one eigenvalue (\mathbf{r}_1) is positive and the other (\mathbf{r}_2) is negative, then from relation 12 we can derive the algebraic expression of the *saddle path* (HH' in Figure 1) in terms of the *adjusted status coefficient* (β_{i2}) of each member (i) for the economy's negative eigenvalue (\mathbf{r}_2), by setting $\mathbf{n}_1 = 0$ in that relation—this condition ($\mathbf{n}_1 = 0$) neutralizes the (divergent) effect of the positive root (\mathbf{r}_1) on the state variables and thus implies that the economy moves along the (convergent) *saddle path* of the system—as follows:

$$(15) \quad N_i = \mathcal{N}_i + \beta_{i2}(N_j - \mathcal{N}_j) \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

The expression in parentheses is termed the *wealth privilege* (denoted as \mathcal{W}_j) of agent j, i.e. $\mathcal{W}_j = N_j - \mathcal{N}_j$

8. By equations 15, we infer the necessary initial condition for a *high-motivation leisure-oriented* economy ($\mathbf{b}_j > \mathbf{a}_j \mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j < 0$) to grow in the long run:

$$(16.a) \quad N_i(0) > \mathcal{N}_i + \beta_{i2} [N_j(0) - \mathcal{N}_j] \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

where $\beta_{i2} > 0$ for each member (i), because $r_2 < 0$. The difference inside the brackets, $N_j(0) - \mathcal{N}_j$, is termed the *endowment privilege*, denoted as $\mathcal{W}_j(0)$, of member j. In this context, relation 16.a implies that for a *high-motivation leisure-oriented* economy to grow in the long run, the *endowment privilege* of each member (i) must be higher than the product of this member's *adjusted status coefficient* (β_{i2})—for the economy's negative eigenvalue ($r_2 < 0$)—and the other member's *endowment privilege*:

$$(16.b) \quad \mathcal{W}_i(0) > \beta_{i2} \mathcal{W}_j(0) \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

9. A historical example of temporary improvement in an economy's indebtedness before it worsens over the long term is the EU27 economy from 2005 to 2022: The government debt-to-GDP ratio in the EU27 decreased from 42% in 2005, to 39% in 2006, to 35% in 2007, and then increased to 38% in 2007, to 47% in 2008, to 53% in 2009 (IMF 2010), and so on, until reaching an all-time high of 90.8% in 2022 (Eurostat 2024), which is 150% higher than the 60% threshold for this ratio according to the Maastricht criterion.
10. A well-known example of a closed *low-motivation leisure-oriented* economy is that of the USSR during the Cold War, when the Soviet economy was characterized by a combination of low indebtedness and technological and economic stagnation in consumer goods production—despite notable achievements in athletics, the performing arts, and other leisure (cultural) activities. Another example is the barter-based closed economies of continental Europe in the Middle Ages, characterized by economic intertemporal stagnation within the spiritually (religiously) oriented medieval kingdoms of that era.
11. The autonomous system of differential equations for modeling an open laissez-faire economy (relation 7) can be expressed in the following matrix form, where vectors \mathbf{N} , \mathbf{g} and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$, as well as matrix \mathbf{A} , are specified in relation 10:

$$(17) \quad \dot{\mathbf{N}} - \mathbf{AN} = \mathbf{g} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}$$

where \mathbf{N} is specified in relation 11, and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{g} and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ are specified in relation 10.

12. In a closed, *low-motivation, leisure-oriented* economy (Figure 2) that is opening its information borders, the effects of foreign consumption, investment and management standards are both direct and indirect, as described below:
1. **Direct Effect:** As shown in Figure 6.a, the impact of the (positive) *international information coefficient* (γ_i)—which represents the degree of access each member (i) has to these foreign standards—is illustrated by a shift in the intercept of the member's demarcation line (“ $\dot{N}_i = 0$ ”) with the N_i -axis, from \mathbf{G}_i to $\mathbf{G}_i + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i$ (per relations 3 and 8, respectively). This results in a shift of the demarcation line in the positive direction along the N_i -axis. Consequently, in Figure 6.a, the *stationary point* moves from \mathbf{E}^A (a stable node) to \mathbf{E}^B (also a stable node) in a northeastern direction. At the new stationary point (\mathbf{E}^B), the *stationary net worth* (\mathcal{N}_i) of each member (i) is higher than it was before the country's information borders were opened.
 2. **Indirect Effect:** Moreover, as depicted in Figure 6.b, the opening of information borders may also lead to a significant change in the economy's motivational structure and particularly to an increase in the interaction coefficient (\mathbf{b}_i) of each member (i).

FIGURE 6 (a)

Direct effect of opening a closed economy's information borders:
change in the intercept of the demarcation line of each agent i with the N_i -axis
from G_i to $G_i + \Gamma_i$.

FIGURE 6 (b)

Indirect effect of opening a closed economy's information borders:
increase in the slope of the demarcation line of each agent (i)
with respect to the other agent's axis (N_j -axis).

This increase alters the slope of the member's demarcation line (per Relation 8), making it steeper with respect to the N_j -axis. If the increase is big enough, the stationary point may shift into the third quadrant, e.g., from \mathbf{E}^B (a stable node in the first quadrant) to \mathbf{E}^C (a saddle point in the third quadrant), as shown in Figure 6.b. Therefore, this indirect effect can result in a fundamental change in the economy's motivational structure, from *low-motivation* to *high-motivation*, thus exposing the economy to the risk of a future debt crisis: after the opening of information borders, a *hubris area* may emerge in the graphical depiction of the economy.

In summary, opening the information borders of a closed, *low-motivation, leisure-oriented* economy increases the net worth of both members (sectors) if they maintain their existing motivation structure, as shown in Figure 6.a (for example, as occurred in the economies of China, Qatar, and Dubai since 1980s). However, this opening may expose the economy to a future debt crisis if it leads to a fundamental change in the economy's motivation structure, as shown in Figure 6.b. In a worse-case scenario, the economy may enter a debt spiral if it is positioned at a point (such as \mathbf{W} in Figure 6.b) inside the *hubris area* that will emerge right after the opening (as happened in the Russian economy in 1990s). It is important to note, however, that such a change in the economy's motivational structure, from *low-motivation* to *high-motivation*, will not significantly impact its growth trajectory if the economy is safely positioned outside the *hubris area* (e.g., at point \mathbf{W}' in Figure 6.b) just prior to opening its information borders.

The indirect effect depicted in Figure 6.b, however, is beyond the scope of this paper due to the assumption of constant coefficients, as specified in Relation 1'. Socioeconomic structures with changing reaction coefficients are addressed in a follow-up paper, which employs a comparative dynamics methodology.

In general, a useful insight implied by the current model is that preserving a closed economy's motivation structure (reflecting its cultural value system) may be essential for shielding the economy from potential negative consequences of internationalization.

13. Due to the above *direct effect* (§12), opening the information borders of a closed *low-motivation leisure-oriented* economy causes—without government intervention ($\rho = 0$)—the following increase in the economy's *stationary net worth* ($\mathcal{N}_1 + \mathcal{N}_2$):

$$(18) \quad \Delta(\mathcal{N}_1 + \mathcal{N}_2) = \frac{(\mathbf{b}_1 - \mathbf{a}_1)\gamma_2 + (\mathbf{b}_2 - \mathbf{a}_2)\gamma_1}{\mathbf{a}_1\mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{b}_2}$$

This equation (18) is derived by calculating the economy's net worth ($\mathcal{N}_1 + \mathcal{N}_2$) *before* and *after* the opening of the economy's information borders—according to relations 4 above and 21 below, respectively—and subtracting the former (*before*) from the latter (*after*).

14. Figure 7 plots in the (two-dimensional) N_1N_2 plane—the third dimension is time (t), not depicted in the figure—the shifts in the demarcation lines and the concomitant movement of the stationary point $\mathcal{N}(t)$, where $\mathcal{N}(t)$ is the transpose of $[\mathcal{N}_1(t), \mathcal{N}_2(t)]$, in an open-mixed *low-motivation leisure-oriented* economy that is subject to an expansionary government policy ($\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j < \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i < 0$; $\rho > 0$). The stationary point moves over time—from $\mathcal{N}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}(1)$, $\mathcal{N}(2)$,... at $t = 0, 1, 2$,... respectively—progressively moving further from the origin in a northeastern direction.

In open mixed economies, each demarcation line at a specific time t^* is the locus of all $[N_i(t^*), N_j(t^*)]$ combinations that satisfy relation 9 at that time ($t = t^*$). In Figure 7, this locus is plotted in the N_1N_2 -plane for $t = 0, 1, 2$. The intercepts of the demarcation line of member 1 along the N_1 -axis are at $\mathbf{G}_1 + \Gamma_1$, $\mathbf{G}_1 + \Gamma_1 e^\rho$, $\mathbf{G}_1 + \Gamma_1 e^{2\rho}$,..., and those of the other member's demarcation line along the N_2 -axis are at $\mathbf{G}_2 + \Gamma_2$, $\mathbf{G}_2 + \Gamma_2 e^\rho$, $\mathbf{G}_2 + \Gamma_2 e^{2\rho}$,...

FIGURE 7

Mapping the demarcation lines “ $\dot{N}_i(t) = 0$ ” into the N_1N_2 plane, at $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

In three-dimensional space (N_iN_jt), where the third dimension represents time (t), the set of all demarcation lines intersecting the N_i -axis over time in such economies forms a concave *demarcation surface* (not shown in Figure 7). This surface intersects the N_it -plane along a concave curve. The three-dimensional domain (N_1N_2t) is divided into four subspaces by two such surfaces (one for each member i , or equivalently, one for each N_it -plane). These surfaces intersect along an upward-sloping concave curve in a northeastern direction; this curve is termed the economy's *stationary path*.

In the three-dimensional N_1N_2t -space, the *stationary net worth* point over time—depicted (mapped) as $\mathcal{N}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}(1)$, $\mathcal{N}(2)$, and so on, in the two-dimensional N_1N_2 -space in Figure 7—traces out the economy's *stationary path*, which is mapped as a (reddish) line in the N_1N_2 -space in this figure.

To visualize the dynamics of an open mixed economy in three-dimensional N_1N_2t -space, one can apply the principle of motion pictures. Just as a film consists of sequential still frames of a moving object, the movement of the demarcation lines and the stationary point of an open mixed economy can be broken down into “frames” observed “one by one”. For instance, in an open mixed economy that has a *low-motivation leisure-oriented* structure, each frame, placed successively one upon the other, resembles Figure 2 and differs from adjacent frames by the intercept of each demarcation line and also by the stationary point (where these lines intersect). Consequently, the stationary point can be treated as a moving point tracing the *stationary path* of the system through space. Thus, by “freezing the action,” one can determine the exact value of the stationary net worth, $\mathcal{N}_i(t)$, for each member (i) at a specific time (t), as detailed in equations 19-20 below.

15. Setting $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{w}_i - I_i$ in function (1'), we determine the point $[\mathcal{N}_i(t), \mathcal{N}_j(t)]$ where the demarcation lines intersect as they shift over time (t) in an open mixed economy:

$$(19) \quad \mathcal{N}_i(t) = \frac{\mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{g}_j - \mathbf{a}_j \mathbf{g}_i}{\mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j} + \frac{\mathbf{b}_i \gamma_j - (\mathbf{a}_j - \boldsymbol{\rho}) \gamma_i}{(\mathbf{a}_i - \boldsymbol{\rho})(\mathbf{a}_j - \boldsymbol{\rho}) - \mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j} e^{\boldsymbol{\rho} t} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

or equivalently in compact form:

$$(20) \quad \mathcal{N}_i(t) = \mathcal{N}_i + \mathbf{P}_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}) e^{\boldsymbol{\rho} t} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

where \mathcal{N}_i is specified in relation 4—the stationary point of a closed economy—and $\mathbf{P}_i(\boldsymbol{\rho})$ is the coefficient (a ratio) of $e^{\boldsymbol{\rho} t}$ in relation 19. In an open mixed economy, this point moves over time as stated by relations 19-20 (see also §14 above). The first term (\mathcal{N}_i) on the right side of equations 20 indicates that in an open mixed economy, a sufficient condition for the stationary net worth $\mathcal{N}_i(t)$ of each member (i) over time (t) to approach infinity is that the demonstration effect equals the intrinsic effect. It is noteworthy that if we set $\boldsymbol{\rho} = 0$ in relation 19, these equations reduce to the equations for the stationary point in open laissez-faire economies, i.e.:

$$(21) \quad \mathcal{N}_i = \frac{\mathbf{b}_i(\mathbf{g}_j + \gamma_j) - \mathbf{a}_j(\mathbf{g}_i + \gamma_i)}{\mathbf{a}_i \mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{b}_i \mathbf{b}_j} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

16. The general solution of the non-autonomous system of an open mixed economy (relations 1' and 10) may be expressed as follows:

$$(22) \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{N}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{N}_1(t) \\ \mathcal{N}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{11} & \boldsymbol{\beta}_{12} \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1(t) e^{\mathbf{r}_1 t} \\ \mathbf{n}_2(t) e^{\mathbf{r}_2 t} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{n}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = (\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2) / \boldsymbol{\beta}_{11} & -(\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_1) \\ -(\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2) / \boldsymbol{\beta}_{11} & \mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{r}_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N}_1(0) - \mathcal{N}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{N}_2(0) - \mathcal{N}_2(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\mathcal{N}_1(t)$ and $\mathcal{N}_2(t)$ are specified in relations 19-20.

17. In line with the definition of *socioeconomic measure* (Chapter VI), the general definition of *measure* is articulated epigrammatically as:

Measure is a condition of balancing internal trends and external influences,
 fostering an environment conducive to cultural development.

The general definition of measure reflects (1) a fundamental law of nature, whereby a system's internal forces (e.g., blood pressure) balance out the environment's qualitatively similar forces (e.g., atmospheric pressure) exerted on the system, which ceases to exist as soon as it deviates from such balancing equilibrium beyond a quantifiable range of variation (Kant 1786), and (2) the Aristotelian view of leisure for personal and cultural development as a precondition for the realization of the potential of both the individual and the society (Aristotle, *Politics* 8.1338a:1-45; 8.1338b:1-4).

18. If a *closed* or *open laissez-faire* economy is *positively balanced*, the *basin of attraction* is the entire two-dimensional space of potential initial vectors. The *attractor* is the demarcation line " $\mathcal{N}_i = 0$ " of the member (i) with the *lower* status coefficient ($\mathbf{B}_i < \mathbf{B}_j$).

Every trajectory will converge asymptotically to this line, whose slope is \mathbf{B}_i . If the two status coefficients are equal ($\mathbf{B}_i = \mathbf{B}_j$), then the attractor is the equidistant line between the two demarcation lines of the system, i.e., the line $N_i = 0.5(\mathbf{G}_i + \mathbf{S}_j) + \mathbf{B}_i N_j$ in a *closed* economy, or the line $N_i = 0.5(\mathbf{G}_i + \mathbf{S}_j + \mathbf{\Gamma}_i) + \mathbf{B}_i N_j$ in an open laissez-faire economy, where $(i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$ and:

$$(23) \quad \mathbf{S}_i = -(\mathbf{g}_i / \mathbf{a}_i) \quad (i = 1, 2)$$

Graphically, \mathbf{S}_j , termed *socioteleonomial standard* of member j , is represented by a point on the N_j -axis at which the “ $\dot{N}_i = 0$ ” demarcation line intersects this axis.

Similarly, if an *open mixed* economy is *positively balanced*, the basin of attraction is the entire three-dimensional space of potential vectors $[N_i(t), N_j(t)]$, where the third dimension is time (t). The attractor in such an economy is the *demarcation surface*—see §14 above—of the member with the *lower* status coefficient.

19. Algebraically, in *positively balanced* economies the *relative* net worth of each member (i) is a percentage that over time (t) tends to the member's status coefficient, or, equivalently, to the slope of the member's demarcation line, as shown in Figure 3:

$$(24.a) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{N_i(t)}{N_j(t)} \right) = \mathbf{B}_i \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

Therefore, by relation 24.a, the (percentage) share of each member (i) in the economy's net worth, tends over time to the ratio $\mathbf{B}_i / (\mathbf{B}_i + 1)$, given that $\mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{B}_j = 1$ in such economies:

$$(24.b) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{N_i(t)}{N_i(t) + N_j(t)} \right) =$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_j(t)}{N_i(t)}} \right) = \frac{1}{1 + \mathbf{B}_j} = \frac{\mathbf{B}_i}{\mathbf{B}_i + 1}$$

20. By relation 22, we may derive the rate of change in the economy's net worth at point in time (t) as follows, where $[N_i(t) + N_j(t)]'$ is the derivative of $N_i(t) + N_j(t)$ with respect to time:

$$(25.a) \quad \frac{[N_i(t) + N_j(t)]'}{N_i(t) + N_j(t)} =$$

$$\frac{\rho[P_i(\rho) + P_j(\rho)]e^{\rho t} + \mathbf{r}_1(\beta_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 e^{\mathbf{r}_1 t} + \mathbf{r}_2(\beta_{i2} + 1)\mathbf{n}_2 e^{\mathbf{r}_2 t}}{\mathcal{N}_i + \mathcal{N}_j + [P_i(\rho) + P_j(\rho)]e^{\rho t} + (\beta_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 e^{\mathbf{r}_1 t} + (\beta_{i2} + 1)\mathbf{n}_2 e^{\mathbf{r}_2 t}} =$$

$$(25.b) \quad \frac{\rho[P_i(\rho) + P_j(\rho)]e^{(\rho - \mathbf{r}_1)t} + \mathbf{r}_1(\beta_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 + \mathbf{r}_2(\beta_{i2} + 1)\mathbf{n}_2 e^{(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1)t}}{(\mathcal{N}_i + \mathcal{N}_j)e^{-\mathbf{r}_1 t} + [P_i(\rho) + P_j(\rho)]e^{(\rho - \mathbf{r}_1)t} + (\beta_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 + (\beta_{i2} + 1)\mathbf{n}_2 e^{(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1)t}}$$

If \mathbf{r}_1 is the higher eigenvalue and is greater than the *policy factor* (i.e., $\mathbf{r}_1 > \mathbf{r}_2, \rho$), then the limit of that ratio (relation 25.b), as $t \rightarrow \infty$, is equal to that eigenvalue (\mathbf{r}_1):

$$(26) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{[N_i(t) + N_j(t)]'}{N_i(t) + N_j(t)} \right) = \frac{0 + \mathbf{r}_1(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 + 0}{0 + 0 + (\boldsymbol{\beta}_{i1} + 1)\mathbf{n}_1 + 0} = \mathbf{r}_1$$

By relation 13, in *positively balanced* economies, where $\mathbf{a}_1\mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{b}_2$ and $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2 < 0$, the higher eigenvalue is equal to zero, i.e., $\mathbf{r}_1 = 0$, while the lower eigenvalue is negative as \mathbf{r}_2 equals the trace of the matrix (\mathbf{A}) of the system's coefficients—the sum of coefficients in the first diagonal of \mathbf{A} , which is specified in relation 10—i.e., $\mathbf{r}_2 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2 < 0$. Therefore, by relation 26, the growth rate in *positively balanced* economies, is positive, approaching zero asymptotically (from above) over time, whether they are closed or open laissez-faire economies, or even open mixed economies with contractionary or neutral government policies ($\boldsymbol{\rho} \leq 0$):

$$(27) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{[N_i(t) + N_j(t)]'}{N_i(t) + N_j(t)} \right) = 0^+$$

Regarding open mixed economies with expansionary government policies (where $\boldsymbol{\rho} > 0$), if the higher eigenvalue (\mathbf{r}_1) is less than the *policy factor* (i.e., $\boldsymbol{\rho} > \mathbf{r}_1 > \mathbf{r}_2$), then this limit (relation 26) can be derived similarly. Specifically, by dividing all terms in relation 25.a by $e^{\boldsymbol{\rho}t}$ and taking the limit of every term as $t \rightarrow \infty$, we find that the rate of growth in the net worth of the economy tends asymptotically to $\boldsymbol{\rho}$.

21. In the long run, in a *positively balanced* economy (where $\mathbf{b}_i\mathbf{b}_j = \mathbf{a}_i\mathbf{a}_j$; $\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j < 0$) that is closed, open laissez-faire, or open-mixed where the government policy is contractionary or neutral (i.e., $\boldsymbol{\rho} \leq 0$), the values of the state variables (N_i, N_j) increase at the same rate as this rate approaches zero asymptotically from above over time:

$$(28) \quad \text{As } t \rightarrow \infty, \quad \frac{\dot{N}_i(t)}{N_i(t)} \cong \frac{\dot{N}_j(t)}{N_j(t)} \cong \frac{[N_i(t) + N_j(t)]'}{N_i(t) + N_j(t)}$$

In contrast, an economy that is exposed to the risk of a future debt crisis, as depicted by the economy's hubris area, grows at a rate that is equal to the system's *higher* (positive) eigenvalue ($\mathbf{r}_1 > 0$). Consequently, if an exposed economy is trapped within its hubris area, then its indebtedness (negative net worth) will worsen exponentially over time at a rate that approaches this eigenvalue, as specified in relation 26. Only in *positively balanced* economies the *higher* eigenvalue is zero ($\mathbf{r}_1 = 0$).

22. Algebraically, the feasibility condition for *effective* wealth redistribution is specified as follows (where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{i2}$ is defined in relation 12'):

$$(29) \quad |\boldsymbol{\beta}_{i2}| \neq 1 \quad (i = 1, 2)$$

Descriptively, equation (29) states that the absolute value of the *adjusted status coefficient* of each member (i) for the economy's negative eigenvalue (\mathbf{r}_2), must differ from unity in order for *effective* wealth redistribution to be feasible. As the economy moves along the saddle path (HH' in Figure 1) towards its stationary point (\mathbf{E} in Figure 1), the higher [lower] the value of $|\boldsymbol{\beta}_{i2}|$ for a member (i), the more [less] responsive that member is to changes in the net worth of the other member (j), i.e., the greater [smaller] the absolute value of a change in N_i in response to a change in N_j .

23. For an entrapped economy to escape its debt spiral, wealth redistribution should favor the member (sector) with the lower absolute value of the *adjusted status coefficient* for the economy's negative eigenvalue. For example, in Figure 1, *effective* wealth redistribution, repositioning the economy from point W' to point W'' , favors the pauper (the more indebted sector) because $|\beta_{12}| < 1 < |\beta_{22}|$; however, in Figure 8, such redistribution (from point W to point W') favors the prince (the less indebted sector) because $|\beta_{12}| > 1 > |\beta_{22}|$.

It is noteworthy that, from relations (12') and (13), we have: $\mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{b}_2 = (\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{a}_1)(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{a}_2) \Rightarrow \beta_{12} = 1/\beta_{22}$. Thus, if $|\beta_{12}|$ is less [greater] than 1, then $|\beta_{22}|$ is greater [less] than 1.

FIGURE 8

Effective wealth redistribution favoring the privileged member (sector).

24. In a high-motivation economy, the amount of redistributed wealth, $\mathbf{m}_i(t)$, from one member (i) to the other member (j) at a point in time (t), should exceed $\Phi_i(t)$ where:⁹⁹

$$(30) \quad \Phi_i(t) = \frac{\mathcal{W}_i(t) - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{W}_j(t)}{(1 + \beta_{i2})} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

Here, $\mathcal{W}_i(t)$ represents the *wealth privilege* of member i at time t (see also §7 above), i.e., $\mathcal{W}_i(t) = N_i(t) - \mathcal{N}_i$ in closed economies or open laissez-faire economies, where \mathcal{N}_i is specified by relations (4) and (21) respectively; in open mixed economies, $\mathcal{W}_i(t) = N_i(t) - \mathcal{N}_i(t)$, where $\mathcal{N}_i(t)$ is specified by relations 19-20. At the initial time (t=0), the *wealth privilege*, $\mathcal{W}_i(t)$, of member i is equivalent to this member's *endowment privilege*, $\mathcal{W}_i(0)$, as specified in §8.

The economic interpretation of $\Phi_i(t)$ is the amount of wealth redistribution from member i to member j (at time t), that would reposition an entrapped economy from inside the hubris area to a point on the saddle path. For example, in Figure 4, redistribution of $\Phi_i(t)$, from point W (inside this area) to point ϕ on the saddle path, would achieve this. The point ϕ is the intersection of the saddle path and the *wealth-redistribution line*, which

text continued to page xv >>>

FIGURE 9
High-Motivation Work-Oriented Economy.

FIGURE 10
Low-Motivation Work-Oriented Economy.

FIGURE 11
Negatively Balanced Economy.

FIGURE 12
Totally Neutral Economy.

>>> text continued from page xii:

forms a 135° angle with the horizontal axis and passes through the entrapped economy's position (\mathbf{W} in Figure 4) inside the hubris area. For wealth redistribution to be effective, it must exceed $\Phi_i(t)$ by a marginal amount (u), i.e., $\mathbf{m}_i(t) = \Phi_i(t) + u$.

To derive relation 30 algebraically, we combine the equation of the saddle path, $N_i = \mathcal{N}_i + \beta_{i2}(N_j - \mathcal{N}_j)$, from relation 15, with the equation of the downward-sloping 135°-line, $N_i = N_i(t) + N_j(t) - N_j$, equating the left-hand sides of both equations, solving for N_j and subtracting $N_j(t)$ from the resulting expression for N_j .

The specification of $\Phi_i(t)$ in relation 30 is applicable to most economies exposed to the risk of future debt spirals, i.e., to *high-motivation* economies—whether *leisure-oriented* (Figure 1), or *work-oriented* (Figure 9), or *partially neutral*, or *totally neutral* (Figure 12), or *counteractive*—as well as to *low-motivation work-oriented* economies (Figure 10).

FIGURE 13
Charybdisic (purple) Path of Ineffective Wealth Redistributions

25. If wealth redistribution $[\mathbf{m}_i(t)]$ is relatively mild in an entrapped high-motivation economy, i.e., if $\mathbf{m}_i(t) < \Phi_i(t)$, where $\Phi_i(t)$ is specified in relation 30, or implemented gradually in successive stages—such as in the *charybdisic* path from point $\mathbf{W}(t)$ to point $\mathbf{W}(t + 2v)'$ inside the hubris area in Figure 13—it will fail to extricate the economy from its debt spiral. Instead, in this figure, an *effective* wealth distribution could reposition the economy from point $\mathbf{W}(t)$ inside the hubris area to point $\hat{\mathbf{W}}(t)$ outside it, instantaneously at time t .
26. In an entrapped economy where the *adjusted status coefficient* (β_{i2}) of the underprivileged agent (i) is lower in absolute value than that of the privileged agent (j), a policy of wealth redistribution in favor of the former (i) will be *cohesively effective*—i.e., it will reposition the economy outside the *hubris area*, while preserving the economy's *class structure* at time t —provided the following condition holds (as in Figure 4):

$$(31) \quad \mathcal{N}(t) > \frac{\mathcal{N}_i - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{N}_j}{1 - \beta_{i2}} \quad (i, j) \in \{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$$

where $\mathcal{N}(t) = [N_i(t) + N_j(t)]/2$, i.e., $\mathcal{N}(t)$ is the economy's *average net worth* at time t . If the above condition (relation 31) holds, then:

$$(32) \quad \Phi_j(t) < \mathcal{N}(t) - N_i(t)$$

where $\Phi_j(t)$ represents the redistributed net wealth, as specified in relation 30. Consequently, if this condition (relation 31) is satisfied, a *cohesively effective* wealth redistribution $\mathbf{m}_j(t)$ will reposition the economy at a point, such as \mathbf{W}' in Figure 4, along the downward-sloping *wealth-redistribution* line between its intersections (ϕ) with the *saddle path* and (η) with the *egalitarian-distribution* line, i.e.:

$$(32') \quad \Phi_j(t) < \mathbf{m}_j(t) < \mathcal{N}(t) - N_i(t)$$

27. The ratios on the right-hand side of relation 31 represent each member's net worth, termed *saddle-path egalitarian wealth*, corresponding to the *saddle-path egalitarian point* (δ in Figures 4–5). These ratios are equal:

$$(33) \quad \frac{\mathcal{N}_i - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{N}_j}{1 - \beta_{i2}} = \frac{\mathcal{N}_j - \beta_{j2}\mathcal{N}_i}{1 - \beta_{j2}}$$

28. If the condition specified relation 31 does not hold in an entrapped economy, where the *adjusted status coefficient* (β_{i2}) of the underprivileged agent (i) is lower in absolute value than that of the privileged agent (j), a policy of wealth redistribution alone—without any debt reduction—cannot be *cohesively effective*. This is because it would either reposition the economy outside the hubris area disrupting its class structure at time t (e.g., from point \mathbf{W} to point \mathbf{W}'' in Figure 5), or it would reposition the economy inside the hubris area preserving the class structure but failing to escape the trap (as from point $\mathbf{W}(t)$ to point $\mathbf{W}(t)'$ in Figure 13). In the first case, the redistribution is effective but not cohesive; in the second, it is cohesive but not effective.

Instead, a specific policy mix—combining wealth redistribution and debt reduction—will be *cohesively effective* with *minimized* loss to creditors, if it implements the following three actions simultaneously and instantaneously at this time (t):

1. **Wealth redistribution** of net amount $\Psi_j(t)$ from sector j to sector i , where:

$$(34) \quad \Psi_j(t) = N_j(t) - \frac{\mathcal{N}_j - \beta_{j2}\mathcal{N}_i}{1 - \beta_{j2}}$$

2. **Debt reduction** of amount $\Omega_i(t)$ in favor of sector i , where:

$$(35) \quad \Omega_i(t) = \frac{2(\mathcal{N}_i - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{N}_j)}{1 - \beta_{i2}} - 2\mathcal{N}(t)$$

3. **Debt reduction** of a marginal amount u (e.g. \$1) in favor of sector j .

29. The creditors' total loss due to *comprehensive debt reduction*, amounts to $\Omega_i(t) + u$, where $\Omega_i(t)$ and u are specified above (§28). This loss is *minimized*: all other alternative combinations of wealth redistribution and debt reduction, that would enable the entrapped economy to escape the hubris area while preserving its socioeconomic class structure, result in a greater total loss for the creditors. Therefore, from their perspective, it is to their best interest to forgive (write off) this debt overhang, $\Omega_i(t) + u$, rather than finance it.

Conditions of *Effective Debt Crisis Management*

FIGURE 14

Algorithm for Relativist Debt Crisis Management in High-Motivation Economies.

30. As a result of a *comprehensive debt reduction* in a debt-ridden economy at time t , where the *adjusted status coefficient* (β_{i2}) of the underprivileged sector (i) is lower in absolute value than that of the privileged sector (j), and the economy's *average net worth* falls short of its *saddle-path egalitarian wealth* (that is specified in §27 above), the net worth of the former sector, $N_i(t+v)$, and that of the latter sector, $N_j(t+v)$, where v is infinitesimally small, are specified as follows (by relations 33-35):

$$(36.a) \quad N_i(t+v) = \frac{\mathcal{N}_i - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{N}_j}{1 - \beta_{i2}}$$

$$(36.b) \quad N_j(t+v) = \frac{\mathcal{N}_j - \beta_{j2}\mathcal{N}_i}{1 - \beta_{j2}} + \mathbf{u} = \frac{\mathcal{N}_i - \beta_{i2}\mathcal{N}_j}{1 - \beta_{i2}} + \mathbf{u}$$

That is, the net worth of the underprivileged sector becomes exactly equal to the *saddle-path egalitarian wealth* of the economy, and the net worth of the privileged sector exceeds this amount only by a marginal amount (\mathbf{u}), of rather symbolic significance. Consequently, the economy becomes *temporarily* egalitarian at time $t+v$.

31. The algorithm for relativist debt crisis management (Figure 14) includes the special case of an entrapped economy with $|\beta_{i2}| = 1$, where only unconditional debt reduction (*without* wealth redistribution) can enable the economy to escape its debt trap at a specific point in time t , because the *wealth-redistribution* line and the *saddle path* are parallel. The necessary debt reduction—that minimizes creditor loss—amounts to a *total* of $\Omega(t) + \mathbf{u}$, where \mathbf{u} is defined above (§28) and:

$$(37) \quad \Omega(t) = -\mathcal{W}_i'(t) + \beta_{i2}\mathcal{W}_j'(t) = -\mathcal{W}_j'(t) + \beta_{j2}\mathcal{W}_i'(t)$$

If $N_j(t)$ is greater than the *saddle-path egalitarian wealth*, then the debt reduction should favor either sector (i or/and j); if $N_j(t)$ is less than *saddle-path egalitarian wealth*, then the debt reduction should favor the privileged sector (j) or both sectors (i and j).

32. As specified in the algorithm above (Figure 14), if the the *saddle path* of an entrapped economy passes through the intersection (point η in Figures 4-5) of the *wealth-redistribution* line with the *egalitarian-distribution* line, then no significant debt reduction is required to enable the economy to escape its debt trap. Instead, an egalitarian wealth redistribution (without debt reduction) of amount $\Psi_j(t)$ from the privileged sector (j) to the underprivileged sector (i) at a specific point in time t will reposition the economy on the *saddle path*—at the intesection (η), termed the economy's *egalitarian point*—where:

$$(38) \quad \Psi_j(t) = \frac{N_j(t) - N_i(t)}{2}$$

Then only an insignificant debt reduction \mathbf{u} (e.g., \$1 in this model), in favor of the privileged sector (j), will suffice to reposition the economy outside the hubris area, while maintaining the class structure of the economy, at a creditor loss that is thus minimal (symbolic).

33. Relations 36.a-b suggest that, in peacetime, *temporary* egalitarian policies of wealth redistribution may enable an economy to escape its debt trap at minimized creditor loss. Likewise, in wartime, irrespective of an economy's structure, its transition from a peace economy to a war economy involves significant economic and social restructuring aimed at maximizing resource allocation and public support for the war effort. More specifically in wartime, *temporary* egalitarian policies—such as horizontal food rationing, progressive taxation, and restrictions on luxury imports during the war—play a critical role in ensuring

fairness and social cohesion. These *temporary* egalitarian measures (a) promote unity and morale, (b) prioritize resource allocation for essential war needs rather than private consumption, and (c) prevent economic inequality and inflation, e.g., as seen in the economies of the Winning Powers during the Second World War ([Rockoff 1998](#); [Edgerton 2011](#)).